

SOCIAL SCIENCES

ONLINE TEACHING DURING THE COVID 19 PANDEMIC IN UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

This study shows the challenges faced by students during the covid 19 school period. The transition from traditional face-to-face teaching to online teaching has also been a challenge. Students, like the entire population, were isolated during the pandemic and were forced from the conditions to start online learning. This change in teaching was accompanied by many problems. Starting from the lack of personal computers, Internet connection, etc. But in addition to the infrastructure, the students also encountered psychological problems due to the isolation.

Keywords: Student, covid-19, Albania, psychological, technology.

1. Introduction

Albania is located in the southwestern part of the Balkan peninsula [1]. With the outbreak of the pandemic in Albania, the Ministry of Education was forced to close all levels of education[2] and everyone from first grade to university was forced to attend online classes.

This study tries to present the difficulties faced by students during online learning. Online studies are thought to be much cheaper than traditional education. So, we do not have the costs of transportation, accommodation, living away from family, etc. that are saved. But students are also encountered

with other psychological difficulties . By isolating themselves, they began to increase the level of stress they were experiencing. Various studies have shown sleep problems that the students had during the period of the blockade due to covid 19 [3]. Also the problems of depression in students.[4]

2. Theoretical Framework

Transition of teaching from the traditional method in the online one, it has also increased the stress among the teaching staff [5]. As Rieley, J. B. (2020) points out, online learning is emerging as a major victory amid this chaos [6] Most of the terms (online learning, open learning, web-based learning, computer-mediated learning, blended learning, m-learning, for ex.) have in common the ability to use a computer connected to a network, that offer the possibility to learn from anywhere, anytime, in any rhythm, with any means[7].

In general, a complete online course requires a detailed lesson plan design, learning materials such as audio and video content, and technology support teams [8].

As points out, Shivangi [6]. There are a number of technologies available for online education, but sometimes they create many difficulties. These difficulties and problems associated with modern technology range from download errors, installation issues - login problems, audio and video problems, etc. Sometimes it seems to the student that online teaching is boring and unbearable. Online learning has so much time and flexibility that students never find time to do it. Personal attention is also a big issue facing online learning. Students want two-way interaction which sometimes becomes difficult to implement.

1. Methodology

This study used qualitative methodology. When researchers have little information and require rigorous exploration of the research problem learning from participants, qualitative research is appropriate [9].

For this study, 11 interviews were conducted, with people who are involved in the construction of these facilities in this area. Participants were randomly selected within this framework. The questions were combined, there were closed questions but also open questions. Open questions were used in order to give the interviewees the opportunity to describe new information about the topics that were of interest. These research interviews lasted between 20 and 25 minutes. They were assured that any information they shared would be kept confidential. To protect their identity, we do not mention their names.

After the interviews, which were recorded, began their transcription and manual coding in vivo[10].

1. Result

Lack of infrastructure for online learning, it also appears during the interview. This is how one student emphasizes, among other things because I didn't have a personal computer and I couldn't follow the online course.

And one student emphasizes the difficulty of following the online course there was no internet in the area where I lived and the only way was with a smartphone where the cost of the internet was too high to afford.

Besides the technological infrastructure problem there was also the lack of spaces at home where the students could follow the lesson in peace. Not all students had the necessary spaces in the apartments where they lived. This is how one student emphasizes, among other things. That my family lives in a small apartment and I had difficulty following the lesson calmly that there would always be someone from the family who would enter the room.

But another student emphasizes besides me, there was also my brother who was going to teach online

and we didn't have the necessary space in the family where we could study in peace. And I often conflicted with my brother because I had to go to the room to study.

But in addition to the infrastructure for online learning, students at first I encountered the difficulties

of the program where the lesson took place, for his discharge, disconnection, registration in this program.

For this, a student emphasizes that the beginning of online learning was difficult,

how we learned to download the program and register. It was a complicated procedure because we had never developed online learning. This situation was also among the teachers who were not used to this method and they encountered these difficulties. And not having the proper training, they found it difficult to help the students.

A student among other things, it states that the difficulty to connect to the program remained among others that even the teachers themselves had a hard time for themselves and they could not guide us in detail about these procedures.

But in addition to this, students also encountered an increase in depression and loneliness during online learning.

A student other honors says . That online learning at the beginning it was difficult as we learned, but with the problem that we didn't get used to it was the loneliness we experienced during the online lesson. This made me feel sad all the time.

Another student emphasizes that because of alone, where during the university I was used to socializing, I started to feel a state of depression, where it seemed to me that this state would never end.

Discussion:

This qualitative study highlight the students' problems during online learning, they had logistical problems with personal computers and even space in the apartments where they lived.

Jobs in the distance requires access to digital technology such as computer, and a stable and reliable Internet connection.

Many of the standards and some local staff in the village, and we had no problems with internet connections. There may be competing requirements for student and academic time and difficulties in accessing the computer. Not all students or staff have their own digital technology and it may be necessary to share with other family members. Another difficulty with working from home is that for many, other members of the household are also at home and childcare is unavailable (schools and day care centers / nurseries are closed[11].

The study shows that the students also had psychological problems who came because of isolation, separation from society. Conventional classroom socialization is another major missing from online learning[12]. In traditional classroom learning, body language, facial expressions and the voice of teachers they are all important teaching tools. However, once a course transitions to online instruction, body language and facial expressions are under limitations as it is difficult to use these tools through screens and only "voice" can fully function [13].

Conclusions:

University in times of crisis such as the isolation due to the covid 19 pandemic, they were able to find it choose through online learning despite many difficulties. Many issues are attached to online education, but we cannot ignore its benefits in times of such crises. [13]

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